

MICROMECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE INITIATION AND PROPAGATION IN CFRP USING SYNCHROTRON RADIATION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Micromechanisms of fatigue damage initiation and propagation in double-notch carbon/epoxy coupons have been investigated using synchrotron radiation computed tomography. The material system used is a particle-toughened system, and the role of the particles has been assessed. The use of *in situ* fatigue experiments and computed tomography allowed insights of the physical mechanisms to be obtained that are not possible to achieve using other methodologies. Observations have shown particles acting mainly to influence damage propagation, causing damage retardation within the resin rich regions. However, particles do not play a significant role in the process of early initiation, where the damage is localised at the fibre/matrix interface. Fibre breaks along 0° ply splits occur due to local buckling or tension failure have been detected for various loads and cycle counts; while fibre breaks in the bulk composite are exclusively associated with high peak loads.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polymers have excellent fatigue resistance in the fibre direction. This derives from the fact that the fibres, which are essentially fatigue resistant, mainly carry the load [1,2]. However, composites are widely used as laminates in engineering design, and damage is seen to initiate at low numbers of cycles [3]. Previous studies have focused on assessing fatigue damage mechanisms and the link to fatigue life using various experimental techniques [4-10]. However, reliable predictions based on physical observations remain key to improve CFRP structural design.

The enhancement of the resin in terms of fracture toughness can be an advantage when these types of matrix are employed in fibre composites. However, the effectiveness achieved for bulk resin has been showed that is not maintained when the epoxy is used as the matrix in composite systems [11]. To date, several approaches to toughening have been developed to a sufficient level of maturity that they are employed in service for CFRPs for aerospace applications; however, the underpinning micromechanisms have not been widely investigated. Consequently, the effectiveness and the optimization of specific toughening systems in terms of damage reduction and fracture toughness remain a relatively empirical process. Furthermore, there has been very little work to understand the consequence of fatigue loading on the effectiveness of these toughening strategies.

Previous work conducted on carbon fibre/epoxy laminated composites using X-ray computed tomography, have demonstrated the power of this technique in assessing damage micromechanisms for small coupons subjected to quasi-static load [12-13], impact [14], and compression after impact [15]. The detail and the accuracy provided using a resolution on the order of 1 µm or less has been shown to be appropriate to capture damage events and their correlation with the local microstructure [12, 16]. Fibre failure under an incremental tensile load for a toughened-particle carbon/epoxy were monitored [17] showing a suddenly acceleration of fibre breaks in the bulk within the notch region for loads higher than ~85% of the quasi-static tensile strength (UTS) and suggesting that failure under a tensile load is associated with fibre cluster formation at high loads (from 95% UTS). This work represents the first evaluation of fibre failure under fatigue for different load conditions, and the main

focus is the identification of the underpinning mechanisms of fibre breaks along the 0° ply splits and in the bulk composite.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material system

A thermoplastic particle toughened M21/T700 carbon/epoxy, with a $[90/0]_s$ layup, was investigated. The material was laid up and autoclaved cured using a standard aerospace cure cycle as specified by the supplier [18]. Double-edge notched specimens with an overall gauge length of 66 mm for the *ex situ* and 34 mm for the *in situ* experiments, 4 mm width and a nominal central cross-section between the notches of 1 mm were prepared from the laminated plates via waterjet cutting, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Geometry and dimensions of the specimens (a), detail of the notch zone (b), specimen with tabs bonded (c), schematic of the region of interest considered during the scans (d).

The different length of the coupons for the *in situ* tests (34 mm) was determined by the requirement to fit the specimens in the portable *in situ* fatigue load frame. Aluminium tabs were attached to the *ex situ* specimen to facilitate the application of a tensile load during the scan [13], see Figure 1(c). The notched tensile strength (UTS) under quasi-static loading was previously measured as 960 MPa across the notch cross-section [13]. Further details on the material system and loading devices are provided in [3,13,19].

2.2 Fatigue experiments

In situ fatigue tests were performed at 50% of the nominal quasi-static tensile failure load using pre-fatigued coupons, in which 700 cycles had been previously applied, at the same load. These were tested using a standard servo-hydraulic load frame at a load ratio of $R=0.1$, and frequency of 5 Hz. An additional 100 cycles were applied using the *in situ* load frame at a lower frequency of ~ 0.1 Hz. Assessment of the fatigue micromechanisms was the focus of these experiments, as such, the resolution used and the full field imaging afforded by synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT) allowed detailed observations to be made with a relatively low number of cycles.

Ex situ fatigue tests were also performed using a servo-hydraulic load frame at a load ratio of $R=0.1$, and frequency of 10 Hz. A peak load of 30% UTS at 200 cycles was used to assess an early stage of fatigue damage initiation; while 30% UTS at 10^6 cycles, 50% UTS at 10^3 and 10^5 cycles, and 70% UTS at 10^3 cycles were used to evaluate the influence of both cycle count and peak load on fibre failure behaviour.

2.3 Synchrotron X-ray procedures

Coupons were scanned at the Swiss Light Source (on the TOMCAT-X02DA Beamline, Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland). Beam energies of 14 keV and 19 keV were used for the *in situ* and *ex situ* specimens respectively. The distance between the specimen and the detector was set on the order of 20-30 mm, providing a degree of phase contrast, consistent with the beam energy used. Coupons for the *ex situ* tests were placed in a tensile load frame [13] and scanned in the loaded state (load applied was ~90% of the maximum peak load in fatigue) to allow identification of narrow cracks, which was found to be particularly useful for the evaluation of the initiation stages damage. Specimens used in the *in situ* fatigue tests were scanned under a tensile load (again ~90% of the maximum peak) at 700 cycles, as a first step, and then again after applying a further 100 cycles, maintaining the same region of interest for the scan, see Figure 1(d).

During each tomographic scan, 1500 projections were collected on a 2560 x 2160 pixel detector, through a rotation of 180°. Different isotropic voxel resolutions were used according to the aim of the investigation: 0.325 µm for the *ex situ* scans performed to assess the damage initiation; 0.69 µm for the *in situ* fatigue tests, and 1.6 µm for the *ex situ* scans used for the fibre failure analysis. High resolutions were used to enhance damage detection during initiation and the micromechanistic assessment, whilst more modest resolutions offer a compromise in terms of improved field-of-view for more representative sampling of material behaviour, and were used for the fibre breaks evaluation. Three-dimensional reconstruction was obtained from radiographs using an in-house (SLS) code based on the GRIDREC/FFT approach [20]. Commercial and open source software, such as VGStudio Max v2.1, FIJI, and Matlab were used for image analysis.

3 FATIGUE DAMAGE

3.1 Fatigue damage modes

Damage modes detected in the cross-ply coupons subjected to fatigue loading are: 0° ply splits starting from the notch region and propagating along the loading direction, transverse ply cracks located in the notch region, delamination at the ply interfaces, and fibre breaks. A three-dimensional rendering of the damage modes observed in these coupons was provided in [3]. This work mainly focuses on the micromechanisms of 0° ply splits and fibre failure. In particular, fibre breaks were observed along the 0° ply splits at different loading conditions (peak loads and cycles), while the fibre breaks in the bulk composite (within the 0° plies) were associated exclusively with peak loads higher than 50% UTS. A summary of the cases investigated, in which fibre failures were counted, is reported in Table 1; where the ‘notch region’ is referred to a length of ~3 mm from the middle of the notch along one side, see Figure 1(d), while the ‘total volume’ is represented by the total imaged volume, which includes all the damage modes detected. This latter was obtained by concatenation of multiple volumes taken at the relevant resolution. The direct comparison between the number of fibre failures can be achieved considering the notch region, which was maintained the same for each loading condition, see Table 1. The number of fibre failures in the ‘total volume’ was used to estimate the fibre breaks density along the 0° ply split length (see Figure 5), and to assess the fibre failure distribution in the bulk composite (see Figure 6).

%UTS	N (Cycles)	Breaks along 0° ply split		Breaks in the bulk composite	
		Notch region	Total volume	Notch region	Total volume
30	10 ⁶	57	57	-	-
50	10 ³	148	148	7	7
50	10 ⁵	325	542	18	33
70	10 ³	363	700	70	107

Table 1: Summary of fibre breaks detected under fatigue loading.

The evaluation of fibre breaks for an equivalent quasi-static case (80% UTS) has been taken into account to assess whether the fibre breaks detected in the fatigue cases are influenced by the cycling process and not by the initial quasi-static (first cycle) load alone. The total number of fibre breaks detected in the quasi-static case was 124 with 14 breaks in the bulk composite. The volume considered was identical to that used to count the fibre breaks in the fatigue case, in terms of dimensions and location (extending 3 mm away from the centre line of the notch). This confirms that the majority of fibre breaks detected in fatigue is due to the cycling process, and it results consistent with the higher number of fibres failed observed at 50% UTS when an increasing number of cycles was considered (Table 1).

3.2 Split initiation and propagation

Fatigue damage initiation has been investigated by the use of *ex situ* tests and high resolution ($0.325\ \mu\text{m}$ voxel size) to resolve narrow cracks. The focus for these tests was on the assessment of the role of toughening particles in damage initiation. The application of a relatively low peak load (30% UTS) and number of cycles (200) was used to initiate damage, which at this early stage is only associated with the fibre-rich regions and no propagation occurs within the resin rich regions. Damage appears as discontinuous: many parallel microcracks initiate following the fibres along the loading direction, separated by the presence of small bridging ligaments (on the order of a few micrometers), Figure 2(a). Toughening particles do not show any debonding or evidence of fracture at this stage.

Figure 2: Fatigue damage initiation detected for a peak load of 30% UTS and 200 cycles (a), *in situ* fatigue damage propagation for a fixed load of 50% UTS at 700 cycles (b) and 800 cycles (c) within the same coupon considering the same cross-section along the load direction [19]. A: fatigue damage propagation as particle debonding; B: bridging ligaments as bulk resin; C: bridging ligaments as toughening particles; D: damage propagation at the fibre/matrix interface.

Fatigue damage propagation was assessed by the same authors using *in situ tests* in previous work [19], and reported here in Figure 2(b) and 2(c), where the same cross-section along the loading direction for two cycles counts is shown: 700 (Figure 2(b)) and 800 (Figure 2(c)) for a fixed peak load

of 50% UTS. Toughening particles play an important role in the process of damage propagation (within the resin rich regions) defining a preferential path for the damage, and creating bridging ligaments along the crack wake. This causes a non-uniform growth of the crack front profile, which results characterised by a lower growth rate in the zones corresponding to the resin rich regions [19]. The damage propagation detected in the fibre-rich regions is smooth and continuous; see Figure 2(b) highlighted with D. As such, the small bridging ligaments (between microcracks) observed in the damage initiation stage (Figure (2a)) appear subject to failure due to ongoing cycling, creating a continuous crack, as shown in Figure 2(b) with D.

The comparison between the micromechanisms of damage initiation and propagation show some similarities, such as the formation of multiple microcracks rather than a dominant continuous crack, and the presence of bridging ligaments between them. However, the lengthscale is different when fibre-packed regions (Figure 2(a)) or resin rich regions (Figure 2(b) and (c)) are considered. This latter case is characterised by the formation of microcracks (echelon cracks), attributable to particle debonds, oriented mainly at 45° with respect to the load direction. Therefore, the geometry of the bridging ligaments is closely related to the inter-particle distance and particle distribution (local microstructure), which result in characteristic dimensions on the order of ~10-100 µm; while the bridging ligaments detected in correspondence of the fibre/matrix interface were of 3-5 µm.

3.3 Micromechanisms of fibre failure along the split

The micromechanisms that lead to fracture of fibres located along the 0° ply split for the particle-toughened system have been investigated by *in situ* fatigue tests. The analysis conducted was aimed not only to count the total number of breaks added due to the additional number of cycles, but also to understand the micromechanisms and to assess whether the increase in the number of breaks occurred in locations that already exhibited fibre breaks or at new nucleation sites. The comparison of the two cyclic conditions (700 and 800) has shown 12 fibre breaks added during the 100 cycles, in addition to the 74 fibre breaks detected at 700 cycles. The gauge length considered in these cases, determined by the voxel resolution chosen, was ~1.5 mm starting from the middle-notch, which roughly corresponds with the geometrical dimension of the notch. The additional fibre breaks detected were located along nearly the entire length of the 0° ply splits and most of them appear as single breaks (10) with only two doublets (two adjacent fractured fibre). Figure 3 illustrates a single fibre obliquely bridging the 0° ply split, which is partially debonded from the matrix due to the propagation of the split, Figure 3(a). The traction associated with the fibre bridging appears to cause local bending of the fibre.

Figure 3: 0° ply split development along the fibre interfaces at 50% UTS and 700 cycles (a), fibre failure along 45° fracture plane at 800 cycles due to local buckling (b).

The additional 100 *in situ* cycles caused the failure of the fibre in the middle of the bridging section, as shown in Figure 3(b). The direction of shear indicated in Figure 3(a) highlights that the failure of the fibre in this case is due to a local buckling process. However, in the same specimen local tensile fibre failures have been observed, an example is reported in Figure 4. In this case the debonding of the bridging fibre results in the opposite orientation relative to the local shear across the split, as showed in Figure 4(a). As the debonding increases during the additional cycling, failure occurs due to the resolved tensile stress, Figure 4(b), which is also indicated by the residual separation of the fibre fracture surfaces in contrast to that shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 4: 0° ply split development along the fibre interfaces at 50% UTS and 700 cycles (a), fibre failure at 800 cycles in tension (b).

The mechanism identified to cause fibre failure along the 0° ply split path is due to the presence of fibre bridges between the two flanks of the split. In both cases, Figure 3 and Figure 4, the fibre failure is associated with a wake process rather than a near-tip process. The comparison between Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows that the fibre breaks due to buckling occur along a direction of 45° with respect to the loading direction, while the fibre breaks due to a tensile event exhibits a fracture plane perpendicular to the loading direction.

The analysis conducted has shown that the new fibre breaks detected along the 0° ply splits occur in ‘new locations’ and not adjacent to pre-existing fibre breaks. The number of fibres failed in tension and in buckling along the 0° ply split is the same (37) at 700 cycles, while the additional fibre breaks obtained at 800 cycles are due mostly to buckling (11) rather than in tension (1). It should be noted that no fibre breaks in the bulk material (away from the crack) were observed for the *in situ* conditions considered (*i.e.* 50% UTS, 700-800 cycles).

3.4 Fibre failure along the 0° ply splits

The number of fibres failed along the 0° ply splits were counted for each loading condition investigated and reported in the Table 1. It is clear that the increase of peak load and number of cycles promotes fibre failure along the split. The distribution of the fibre breaks along the 0° ply splits has been evaluated taking into account the total length of the splits associated with the different loading conditions (variation of load and/or cycles). The crack length was divided into intervals of 0.5 mm and the fibre break density was quantified for each interval. Figure 5 shows the results obtained for the case of 50% UTS at 10³ and 10⁵ cycles; the fibre breaks density plot starts in correspondence of the

crack root (distance 0) and extends towards the crack tip. As expected, while maintaining the same peak load, an increase in cycles results in an increase of crack length, with the length at 10^5 cycles being approximately double that at 10^3 cycles. The comparison of the two cycling conditions in Figure 5 highlights:

- The number of fibre breaks increases from the tip of the split towards to the root for the low number of cycles (10^3), whereas it exhibits a ‘saturated behaviour’ characterised by a roughly consistent fibre break density (~20-25 fibre breaks/segment), along most of the split for the higher number of cycles (10^5).
- In both cases there is a region (~1-1.5 mm) in the immediate wake of the crack tip in which the fibre break density builds up to ‘saturation’ value presumably reflecting a lower crack opening/shear displacement in this region.
- The break density profile detected in the first 1.5 mm of the split is similar for both cycling conditions.
- No fibre breaks have been detected in the region immediately behind (0.5 mm) the crack tip, even for the case that exhibits fibre fracture saturation along the crack length.
- No failed fibres were observed ahead of the crack tip in either case.

Figure 5: Fibre breaks density along the 0° ply split for 50% UTS at 10^3 and 10^5 cycles.

3.5 Fibre failure in the bulk composite

The application of peak loads lower than 50% UTS did not show any fibre breaks in the bulk composite (within the 0° plies and not along/connected with other damage modes). The number of fibre failures counted for the different fatigue cases investigated are reported in the Table 1, as breaks in the bulk composite. The increase in the number of cycles applied causes an increase in fibre breaks in the bulk. At higher loads, such as 70% UTS, there is a significant number of fibre failure in the bulk: 18 fibres failed for 50% UTS at 10^3 cycles compared with 70 breaks at 70% UTS for the same number of cycles (see notch region values in the Table 1). Therefore, the peak load appears to play a significant role in creating fibre failure in the 0° plies.

%UTS	N (Cycles)	1-plet	2-plet	3-plet	4-plet	5-plet
50	10^3	3	2	-	-	-
50	10^5	14	2	-	-	-
70	10^3	30	7	3	3	1

Table 2: Fibre breaks in the bulk composite for different loading conditions.

A noteworthy aspect is represented by the type of fibre failure (*i.e.* single breaks or multiple breaks), and not exclusively by the total number counted. The application of intermediate loads (*e.g.* 50% UTS) results in fibre failures in the bulk; occurring exclusively as singlets and doublets (two adjacent fibre breaks), see Table 2. However, higher peak load, such as 70% UTS, results in cluster formation, with up to five adjacent fibres failed (5-plet in Table 2). The fibre break distribution in the bulk composite, with respect to the presence of the 0° ply splits, is represented in the 3-D rendering in Figure 6 for the most severe loading condition considered (70% UTS and 10^3 cycles). The notch region (in dark grey) was concatenated with an additional volume (in light grey). The remaining volume, located up to 6 mm from the middle of the notch, was not included in Figure 6 to allow for easier visualisation. However, the analysis conducted has shown only two single fibre breaks in the bulk located in this distant region, with the majority of the breaks lying in the volume presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Fibre failure distribution in the bulk composite for the peak load of 70% UTS and 10^3 cycles.

The fibre breaks seem being accumulated mainly in two regions: (i) the notch region located in the first millimetre from the middle of the notch, and (ii) an intermediate region, located at 2-4 mm from the middle of the notch. Further analyses have been conducted to investigate the two locations with higher fibre break density in the bulk. The region immediately between the notches is characterised by the presence of 0° ply splits (represented in red) and by transverse ply cracks (dark grey line perpendicular to the load direction), which involves a local isolation of the 0° plies due to the presence of fully open transverse ply cracks. The intermediate region is characterised by a reduction in cross-

sectional area due to 0° ply splits and delamination. However, this latter is valid for all the volume along the 0° ply splits starting from the delamination site, which corresponds to the position of the transverse ply cracks in the notch region. Therefore, it is likely that the observed distribution of fibre breaks could be associated with a stochastic process, since isolated fibre breaks have been detected immediately next to the notch and from 4 mm onwards. Details of the fatigue damage modes locations for this specific layup and geometry are provided in [3]. Clusters of breaks detected in the bulk are co-planar and the 4-plet and 5-plet clusters, which represent the highest number of adjacent fibre detected, are both close to the ply interface. The presence of transverse ply cracks detected in the notch region does not seem have direct link with the locations of fibre breaks in the bulk composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Synchrotron radiation computed tomography has been used for *ex situ* and *in situ* fatigue experiments exploiting different loading conditions to assess damage initiation and propagation. Results have shown the formation of small microcracks for both processes, with a different lengthscale of the bridging ligaments formed at the fibre/matrix interface and within the resin rich regions.

Fibre breaks were observed along the 0° ply split paths associated with a wake-process of bridging-fibre failure rather than a near-crack tip process. Two different micromechanisms of fibre failure have been detected along the split connected with local buckling and tensile failure respectively, corresponding to the orientation of the bridging fibre with respect to the local stress state. Fibre break density along the 0° ply split length has been evaluated, showing an increasing trend from the tip of the crack towards to the root. The most severe loading conditions considered, such as the case of 50% UTS and 10⁵ cycles with the case of 70% UTS at 10³ cycles, exhibited a 'saturation' in fibre failure density along the split. This is consistent with final fibre break dependency on the fibre distribution/alignment. Fibre failure in the bulk composite (0° plies) was observed for peak loads higher than 50% UTS. Break cluster formation, consisting of co-planar fractures up to 5 adjacent fibres, was prevalent at the higher peak load tested (70% UTS), although the number of these higher order sites was modest.

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